

SAFETY ASSESSMENT OF THE ARTEMISIA RUTIFOLIA STEPH. EX SPRENG

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Abstract: The theses present the results of the conducted research on the analysis of the *Artemisia rutifolia* Steph. ex Spreng. for the content of heavy metals, radionuclides and pesticides. The object of the study is *Artemisia rutifolia* Steph. ex Spreng. grass. The data obtained will be used to develop a quality specification and standardize the plant substance.

Keywords: *Artemisia rutifolia*, heavy metals, radionuclides, pesticides.

Relevance: The drug safety assessment system is based on the analysis of toxicological characteristics and adverse reactions when using the drug. The increasing anthropogenic impacts on the environment inevitably affect the pollution of phytomaterials. This necessitates quality control of medicinal plant raw materials, taking into account environmental safety criteria, since medicines obtained from medicinal plant raw materials may contain toxic xenobiotics, the intake of which, even in small quantities, carries a certain degree of potential danger to human health.

Safety is the basis for reproducible efficacy and safety of herbal medicines, and in order to ensure research standards for herbal medicines, the quality of herbal materials or preparations is of paramount importance.

One of the promising medicinal plants and a valuable source of biologically active substances growing in Kazakhstan is *Artemisia rutifolia* Steph. ex Spreng.. This plant is used in folk medicine as a fungicidal, antibacterial, anthelmintic and antitumor agent.

The purpose of the study: Safety assessment of the *Artemisia rutifolia* Steph. ex Spreng. is necessary for its further use in pharmacy as an AFS.

Research materials and methods: The object of the study was collected from the nearby meadows of the Merken district of the Zhambyl region (N 42°52'27.34", E 73°10'55.36"). Pharmacopoeial and physico-chemical methods were used.

Main results and conclusions: In accordance with the requirements of the State Pharmacopoeia of the Republic of Kazakhstan, the safety indicators of medicinal plant raw materials include the content of heavy metals, pesticides and radionuclides. The specified parameters of the herb *Artemisia rutifolia* Stephen ex Spreng. defined in accordance with the State Pharmacopoeia of the Republic of Kazakhstan, I, vol.1, methodology 2.8 and the standard «Sanitary and epidemiological requirements for radiation safety».

Determination of heavy metals. The test was performed using the Pharmacopoeia method of atomic absorption spectrometry (State Pharmacopoeia of the Republic of Kazakhstan 1, vol.1,2.2.23 methods I, II).

Table 1 – Determination of heavy metals in raw materials *Artemisia rutifolia* Stephen ex Spreng.

The name of the indicators to be determined	The norm according to the ND	Results			ND on test methods
		Test №1	Test №2	Test №3	
Pb	6,0	0,087	0,172	0,121	GOST P 51301-99
Cd	1,0	none	0,013	0,029	GOST P 51301-99
As	0,5	none	none	none	GOST P 26930-86
Hg	0,1	none	none	none	GOST P 26927-86

The method of determining radionuclides in plant raw materials met the requirements of the hygienic standards «Sanitary and epidemiological requirements for radiation safety» dated December 15, 2020 No. 275, approved by the order of the Minister of Health of the Republic of Kazakhstan. The determination of radionuclides was carried out by gamma-scintillation spectrometry.

Table 2 – Determination of radionuclides in raw materials *Artemisia rutifolia* Stephen ex Spreng.

The name of the indicators to be determined	The norm according to the ND	Results			ND on test methods
		Test №1	Test №2	Test №3	
Cs – 137	400	21,5	22,0	20,4	MT № KZ 07.00.00303-2019
Sr – 90	200	10,0	12,0	16,0	MT № KZ 07.00.00304-2019

Determination of pesticides. The test was carried out using gas-liquid chromatography («2.8.13. Residual amount of pesticides» European Pharmacopoeia).

Table 3 – Determination of pesticides in raw materials *Artemisia rutifolia* Stephen ex Spreng.

The name of the raw material	The name of the indicators	Limits of permissible content, mcg/kg	Result, mcg/kg	ND on test methods
<i>Artemisia rutifolia</i> Steph ex Spreng. ground part	α - HCH	no more 0,1 mcg/kg (in total)	not revealed	«2.8.13. Residual amount of pesticides» European Pharmacopoei a 8.0, t. 1.
	β - HCH		not revealed	
	γ - HCH		0.00252	
	In total		0.00252	
	DDE	no more 0.1 mcg/kg (in total)	0.00262	
	DDT		0.00291	
	In total		0.00553	
	Aldrin	not allowed	not revealed	

The results of the study show that the raw materials of *Artemisia rutifolia* Steph ex Spreng. meets the requirements for the amount of heavy metals, radionuclides and pesticides

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